

Current Values of Education and Culture

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ABSTRACT: The natural purpose of an educational institution is to awaken, to wise, cultivating the intellectual skills in the heart of the learner/student, along with his need to learn all his life. School is also important for us as people because it helps the progress of society, increases trust in people and teaches us to make and maintain friendships, and helps us learn how to work together as a team, which is the main foundation of any successful society. Without school, knowledge could not spread as quickly, and our access to new ideas and people could be hampered. A schoolless world would create difficulties and would prevent the dispersion of economic growth, tolerance and appreciation of our fellow human beings. The purpose of the school is to turn mirrors into windows. Nothing can develop our intellect more than a book, yet in the 21st century, it is read less and less because technology has dethroned the book.

KEYWORDS: school, education, culture, skills, book, technology

Introduction. The benefits of education

The American writer Ellen G. White wrote that: "Our ideas of education take too narrow and too low a range. There is need of a broader scope, a higher aim. True education means more than the pursuit of a certain course of study. It means more than a preparation for the life that now is. It has to do with the whole being, and with the whole period of existence possible to man. It is the harmonious development of the physical, the mental, and the spiritual powers. It prepares the student for the joy of service in this world and for the higher joy of wider service in the world to come"(White 2001,9).

Looking at these things from a Christian perspective: "The source of such an education is brought to view in these words of Holy Writ, pointing to the Infinite One: In Him "are hid all the treasures of wisdom." (Bible, KJV, Colossians 2,3). "He hath counsel and understanding." (Bible, KJV, Job 12:13.). "In a knowledge of God all true knowledge and real development have their source. Wherever we turn, in the physical, the mental, or the spiritual realm; in whatever we behold, apart from the blight of sin, this knowledge is revealed. Whatever line of investigation we pursue, with a sincere purpose to arrive at truth, we are brought in touch with the unseen, mighty Intelligence that is working in and through all. The mind of man is brought into communion with the mind of God, the finite with the Infinite. The effect of such communion on body and mind and soul is beyond estimate. In this communion is found the highest education. It is God's own method of development" (White 2001, 9-10).

The natural purpose of the school is not to teach, but first of all, to awaken by cultivating the intellectual skills in the heart of the student, the need to learn all their life, as Ioan Slavici said. While the first years of school are often greeted with tears and dissatisfaction, etc., it is our civic duty as parents, but also as human beings to educate our children, and ourselves. The school serves a number of purposes, including building trust, teaching children about the importance of teamwork and working with others. The school helps young people to guide themselves the establishment of a daily routine, which is extremely important, as they are directed to their job, to become productive members of society. Students are given access to new ideas, including science and language, and are given the opportunity to learn more about world cultures, geography, and history.

There are many types of schools available, from public to private, homeschooling, online academies that offer internet-based learning. Whatever the choice would be, a person's schooling

is always more effective, if a positive strengthening is added by parents or guardians. Learning about new disciplines and knowing the skills can help a child or even an adult to grow exponentially. People are "social animals" and need people around them in order to survive. School, be it online, can be a great way to build a network of friends and a similar community. Friendships are not the only important relationships that can be built through school. A school environment offers the chance to learn to work with others, which is a very important skill for the real world. All forms of education can lead us to a fulfilling life. There is a job for everyone and perhaps one of the most important reasons to go to school is the wealth of knowledge and information provided within the school, which represents a safe refuge for spreading ideas and often gives us access to topics and ideas which we would not find regularly in our homes or within our friends. Learning a foreign language, for example, is also a good achievement, school is good for everyone and it is important to know that everyone can improve their situation through the act of learning.

School is not only important for us as human beings, but also because it helps at the progress of the society, by educating its members who bring workforce to the individual through the new information acquired within an educational institution. School increases people's trust and teaches us to make and maintain friendships, helps us learn how to work together as a team, which is the main foundation of any successful society. Without school, knowledge could not spread as quickly, and our access to new ideas and people could be easily hampered. A schoolless world would create difficulties and prevent the dispersion of economic growth, tolerance and appreciation of our fellow human beings. For those who are currently enrolled in school, keep it that way, because the whole purpose of education is to turn mirrors into windows.

Comenius said that for every man "life is a school from the cradle to the grave," which would mean that man learns all his life, in search of personal development and self-transcendence. School and professional guidance represent a system of socio-educational actions aiming at the proper integration of each person in society. Ion Heliade Rădulescu's statement regarding the importance of school in the formation of an individual is still valid, although some voices claim that the school of life is the one that forms us for the future. Some parents see the school as a laboratory in which the child, once entered, is still subjected to scientific operations, and after them it is assumed that, after a few years, he will become smarter, more learned, more enlightened. Parents in this category show full confidence in the educational institution, without being particularly involved in the activities it carries out. Parents in this category believe that this is why they send their child to school so that he can learn there. The school informs and trains students taking into account certain principles, taking care to evaluate how the objectives have been achieved. Therefore, the school is not the only laboratory in which the child learns, but only one of them, more specialized and more competent in the field of education than others. It is good for the parent to trust the school, but for the child's education to rise to the expected level, he must get involved, he must collaborate with the teaching staff, so that the proposed methods and objectives to be convergent. Furthermore, even if the school of life has an important role in the life of each of us, it has often proved to be insufficient and therefore, the education acquired in the school environment has always represented a very good basis on which to build life experience. For some parents, a good school is the institution in which children are allowed to freely develop their personality. Secondly, regardless of the situation, we must not deny the fact that the school is an educational institution, quite important, with strict rules, which must be respected in such a way that the child to benefit from the best learning.

Also, through school, the child could interact with classmates, integrate into a new social environment, acquire certain practical skills, language learning or computer skills. He will be listened and evaluated regularly so that teachers to be sure that the student had accumulated the amount of knowledge needed to complete each useful period of study in later years. If the parent expresses dissatisfaction with the teacher who teaches the child, and the child becomes aware of this, in a few years, there will be discipline problems created by the child. In conclusion, if the

parent's attitude towards the school and towards the teacher is indifferent or hostile, the child will quickly catch this and will learn to show negativity towards any form of authority. It is important how parents express their feelings towards the school in front of their children. The school can have only two purposes: the first purpose is that of instruction, respectively to give the child the general knowledge he will need to use. The second purpose is to prepare the child for tomorrow and this is actually education, which does not really mean preparation for life, because education is life itself.

Basic education helps us to have certain skills. We can go on a larger arena, where the training received is wider but less deep or from a certain level, we reach a focus on a few basic disciplines, three or four, in which the young person is talented and will specialize in them. There are also systems in which the restriction to a certain curricular area that you can master in detail, on which you can acquire a kind of hyperspecialization or expertise, has shown that it can generate great benefits, both at individual level and at the level of society. No recipe turns out to be perfect, but these ideas should be carefully reflected when considering any kind of change in education. Education is provided by educational institutions, but the tendency is for certain programs to be developed even by other entities, even companies with state or private capital.

There is no shame in taking courses or even attending college even at the age of 60, although very few do so, but no matter how many faculties someone has done up to the age of 30-40-50, it is important to follow the market from which the person in question is part, to learn continuously, to read, to participate in courses, to be involved in debates, to be part of the social networks that are related to his field of interest. The man, as long as he lives, he learns, is the thinking that should follow any of us, every day, and the curiosity for discovering new things should not cease at any age.

The education system teaches you to think

School, college, is essential; it helps you think in a certain way specific to the job and even if you don't learn too much while you are in it, it still forms a certain way of thinking. The college teaches you, tangentially, what the respective profession is facing, namely the theoretical bases, but it will also educate your way of thinking that must be appropriate to the deontology and customs of the science of that specialty. After graduating from college, you are not a specialist, but you are just at the base of a pyramid represented by the professional group you want to enter. You are allowed to look up and aspire higher. College is the beginning, but it is an essential one. Not going to college, it's a shame, it's like spending a lifetime without enjoying classical music. It is true that you could live well without it, but you will lose an essential dimension of life. You don't have to follow a college in order to achieve something, but because you like the subject, the respective field. We as human beings live only once and it is a shame to spend your time with something you do not like, it does not satisfy you, just because your parents or even you think that it gives you better chances because that job is well paid. The world is extremely interesting. You don't have to waste your time with little things, because if you really like something and if you are really good, no matter what you choose to do in the future, you will do well and you will end up being well rewarded financially for what you do, while if you do something with half your heart, just because you have to do it, you will never be good enough and you will be frustrated on top of that. If you don't like your college, either finish it and start another, or simply change your field and move on. Simion Mehedinți said that school means order and careful consideration every moment, and Victor Hugo said that whoever opens a school closes a prison.

Nowadays when the internet is available to anyone, man has a lot of learning tools at his disposal. Beyond online courses or video tutorials, the person can also go to seminars or conferences in the field he is concerned with. It is important to follow the experts in your field of interest, to subscribe to their Facebook pages, to read their blog, and when time allows you to participate in the events in which they are invited as speakers, where if you can not be present in

the hall, you can watch the event live on the internet, if this possibility is also offered, or you can look for the registration of the event. Learning did not over with the end of the school, because people learn as long as they live or at least that would be ideal. Beyond the theoretical knowledge, a new skill can be developed: get your driver's license, learn a new language, get a certification in your field of activity or learn to play a musical instrument, because any new skill is useful and helps to grow self-esteem, helping you become more resourceful and confident on your own.

There is even a list of things to do, a to-do list, which has its useful value because it will help you see things much more structured and organized, achieving with its help prioritization of activities that you have can do. The list can be made daily or can be made for big goals in life, which in their turn can be divided into three categories: things you can do now, things that take time and things for which you need extra skills. This list should always be consulted and what you have already achieved should be checked. In the situation where certain things are more difficult to achieve, you should not be discouraged, yet you should persevere. The purpose of such a list is to keep you always motivated and to put you in a position to always highlight what is truly valuable and important to you and to your life.

Another kind of lesson

Being happy and grateful is part of the treatment for our mental health. Always be positive, happy and always grateful. Happiness is a choice, so you need to focus on the positive aspects of life and look at all the reasons to be grateful. Take time every day, maybe 5-10 minutes, to think of 3-5 things or people you are grateful for. In time, educate your mind to look at things from any situation. Psychologists teach us that happiness is a tool that helps us to be more productive in what we do, so investing in oneself is one of the most effective investments, with guaranteed results and zero losses. Any new thing learned, any book read, any skill acquired, will help you sooner or later and you just must trust your own strength and give yourself the time you need for this type of investment.

Count your good deeds every morning and fill your mind with positive thoughts. This is the secret to being happy and inspired throughout the day. An extremely important thing that should be done to have a beautiful life is not to get stuck in the past, a past that no longer exists and will never exist, and getting stuck in the past can be very harmful both for your present life as well as for your future life. Our past must be seen only as a life lesson and we must gather from it only those lessons that we need in our evolution and that's it. What we have to do is to analyze very correctly the hardships and sufferings of the past and collect from them the lessons we have learned. But we must understand one thing, namely that the people and experiences from the past were necessary to us then, at that moment, in order to learn what we had to learn and to determine ourselves to become stronger, better and wiser.

Let us not insist on condemning people and situations in the past and thinking of them with resentment and repulsion because this way of acting would distract us from learning from the past and at the same time would create an unhappy present. We must understand that life is not built only from pleasant moments, that sometimes quite difficult and unpleasant people and situations appear in our lives, but what we should do is look at those situations as opportunities for our present and future evolution. Once we learn to extract lessons from these situations and think only of those beautiful moments in the past, it will be much easier for us to forgive those people who once hurted us so much and it must be said that only forgiveness is the true release of the past. Until you don't learn to forgive the one who made you wrong, you will certainly not free yourself and you will not find peace in the present. So, learn to give up negative thoughts about your past, leave it behind because that is its place and pay attention only to your present, because only your present really matters and give yourself the chance to be happy every day, living only in the present.

Culture makes you wiser

Culture is par excellence a relationship issue, so it has inevitably proved that it has sometimes been placed after health and economy. Someone said that without culture we can live, but without economy and health, we can't, if you look at things in a very superficial way. Culture, in its very general sense, is found in every gesture and activity of the modern man. Health in today's world, both personal and collective, cannot be sustained without a medical culture. Economics is not an abstract gear, it operates according to certain rules embedded in an economic culture, starting from some very simple and reaching some very sophisticated rules, which ultimately concern us all. It's the same for all other areas of a science-based culture.

The culture of each field has been profoundly influenced by the pandemic, being equal in front of death and divinity, but we do not live our lives in only one way, according to the same material, moral and spiritual demands. We aren't equal in front of life because we differ in culture, and in wealth we differ only at very least. We differ in religious or political behavior, we have different options, also due to culture or due to a tradition that we assume, a tradition that also means culture. We cannot live without culture or civilization. One of the major conclusions would be that the situation of the pandemic has accentuated the previous negative tendencies regarding the cultural consumption, namely the alienation of the public from the culture has been deepened, in the classical sense.

Reading is less and less, and many, especially young people spend a lot of time on the internet. The film won on portals and subscriptions at home. Music and other videos are watched on youtube and on all TV channels, museums make their visit online, book launches are done online. We are witnessing the triumph of the intermediary in communication; the direct meeting is avoided or postponed. The electronic support has become crucial for all cultural activities. The phenomenon is relatively well known, but what is worrying is the fact that we may become so accustomed to such an attitude towards culture, as it was in the pandemic, stuck in a cautious isolation and in a passive attitude, and many of us, more and more, might be convinced that one can live without a major culture, contenting oneself with surrogates and indulging in entertainment.

Culture does not only mean books, paintings, symphonies, sculptures, philosophy, because culture, once named for better clarity, general culture, means knowledge in any field. A man of the third millennium should have at least a general idea of Mendeleev's Table, the most important writers in history, notions of religion, outer space, Michelangelo, Beethoven, some great movies, Shakespeare's play, how a computer works, what Pithagoras' theorem is used for, information about great explorers, great athletes, etc. Any field of culture provides you with ideas, a necessary thinking, fun, routine escape, the ability to live the lives of the characters and many other things that are useful, to home decorating ideas, culinary recipes and suggestions on how to manage relationships with those around you, holiday destinations. Culture is not a fad, something to prance in a discussion with friends or with anyone else, but it is something very necessary and useful. Certainly, culture makes you smarter.

Nowadays, reading is more and more neglected, and the causes that determine the lack of reading are diverse, and opinions are always divided. Some people exigent ascertain that the clutches of technological devices are to blame, while others blame their parents or teachers. Reading can be likened to appetite, just as reading, or the passion for books, must come from the inside, being the result of reading as many books as possible. In the present, the intuitive and attractive support of films and drawings surpasses the bland lines from the books' pages.

For parents who want to cultivate that seed of passion for reading, it is recommended to address several topics and focus on what is of interest for their children. A subject that appeals to the soul can be a solution closer to reading. It may be considered an obsolete, subject, but the impact of those Christian stories is an important part of personal development on all levels. Skeptics regard the soul as just a form of energy that is driven by hormones, while religion

teaches us that the soul is what makes us unique in the divine creation. The books contain events that have left their mark on the souls of many Christians and changed their perception about life.

When you open a book, you are actually opening a new world

Books have become inevitable for mankind, being part of everyone's daily life. A book is your good friend who never leaves you. The books are full of knowledge, perspectives of a happy life, life lessons, love, prayer and useful advices. They have been around for centuries, and without them, today's knowledge about our ancestors, culture, and past civilizations would be non-existent. What would have happened if intellectuals had never documented their studies? Can we reach an age where we no longer need to read? By reading we expose ourselves to new information, ideas, ways to solve a certain problem and methods to reach a certain goal easily. Reading can help you discover new hobbies or explore things you didn't know you would like. Exploration starts with reading and understanding, because reading helps you to understand the world more, to find certain truths much easier, to rationally analyze things or situations. By reading you can find out more things about society and how to adapt to it. If someone is limited by his own imagination, books will come to his aid to solve this problem. Reading broadens horizons, helps people understand what is and what is not possible, giving a glimmer of hope towards good. Studies show that reading substantially reduces stress, develops reason and improves perception of things, helping to maintain a clear memory and increases alert thinking. Reading is also fun, and a good quality book also creates a good mood, but at the same time develops the intellect. Nothing can develop our intellect as the book does, and yet in the 21st century we read less and less because technology has dethroned the book.

Conclusions

Reading has real benefits that readers can fully enjoy. Reading, the book, contributes especially to the enrichment of vocabulary. However, as a conclusion to the needs of education, I present the idea of the American author Ellen G. White, who presents so elegantly that: "Every human being, created in the image of God, is endowed with a power akin to that of the Creator—individuality, power to think and to do. The men in whom this power is developed are the men who bear responsibilities, who are leaders in enterprise, and who influence character. It is the work of true education to develop this power, to train the youth to be thinkers, and not mere reflectors of other men's thought. Instead of confining their study to that which men have said or written, let students be directed to the sources of truth, to the vast fields opened for research in nature and revelation. Let them contemplate the great facts of duty and destiny, and the mind will expand and strengthen. Instead of educated weaklings, institutions of learning may send forth men strong to think and to act, men who are masters and not slaves of circumstances, men who possess breadth of mind, clearness of thought, and the courage of their convictions. Such an education provides more than mental discipline; it provides more than physical training. It strengthens the character, so that truth and uprightness are not sacrificed to selfish desire or worldly ambition. It fortifies the mind against evil. Instead of some master passion becoming a power to destroy, every motive and desire are brought into conformity to the great principles of right. As the perfection of His character is dwelt upon, the mind is renewed, and the soul is re-created in the image of God. What education can be higher than this? What can equal it in value?" (White 2001, 12-13).

References

Ellen G. White. 2001. *Educație [Education]*. Bucharest: Viata si Sanatate Publishing House.
The Holy Bible, King James Version. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.